

Government Funding Scheme and its impact for Small and Medium Enterprises Development in Nigeria: Bayelsa State in Perspective

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Abstract

This paper investigates government funding scheme and its impact for small and medium enterprises development in Nigeria and the research was confined to Bayelsa state. Governments in the world have set out to solve the plights of the people in different means and with the mind of improving the living standard of the citizens and this brought about the introduction of several funding schemes for sustainable development. This development led to the emergence of small and medium enterprises (SMSs) which do exist in every country. Small and medium enterprises have impacted positively in the development and growth of the economies. The essence of (SMSs) is to increase employment generation, advance socio-economic growth, creates mutual linkages with big industries and the improvement of entrepreneurship, improving local savings, bring down the level of poverty in order to firmly hold onto sustainable development. It is with these reasons; governments have brought about the interest of funding and supporting small and medium enterprises programmes in Nigeria and Bayelsa state respectively. The study relied on qualitative approach and relied on content analysis for its findings. The study frames its arguments from the structural-functionalism framework of analysis. It is recommended that; government should encourage and effectively fund small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state; the federal government should enact appropriate policy to strengthen small and medium enterprises in all states.

Keywords: Development; Enterprise; Entrepreneurships; Poverty; SMSs.

Introduction

Governments in alleviating poverty and improving the welfare of its citizens had involved in different forms of funding schemes. As a result of all these interest of improving the standard of living Small and Medium Enterprises emerged and it have greatly contributed to the Nigerian development in terms of employment, growth and development, and marketing of goods and services. The Nigerian government at present is turning to small and medium scale industries and entrepreneurs as a means of developing the economy and solving problems (Latinwo & Ayozie, 2010). A great percentage of all registered companies in Nigeria are constituted by small scale industries and they have been in existence for a long time (p.45).

Some governments have specifically formulated policies to aid the empowering, growth, development and performance of Small and Medium Enterprises, while others have assisted through loans and fiscal incentives (Onugu, 2005). According to Central bank of Nigeria report (2003) SMEs are very important economic catalyst in developing and industrialized countries, in developed countries 98% or more than belong to the small and medium scale sector. In Japan, 80% of industrial labour force is employed by small firms, 50% in Germany and 46% in USA are employed by smaller businesses.

According to the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) developing countries can conquer poverty and inequality by democratizing, deregulating, and liberalizing the integration of global economy. Recent studies have shown that SMEs contribute to over 55% of GDP and over 65% of total employment in high income countries and also that SMEs and informal enterprises account for over 60% of GDP and over 70% of total employment in middle income countries (OECD, 2004). SMEs are important role players in contributing to the transition of agriculture led economies to industrial ones, SMEs help in the absorption of productive resources at all levels of the economy and contribute to the building of flexible economic system in which small and large firms are interlinked (Fida, 2008). Kongolo (2010) posited that SMEs are responsible for the growing forces of the largest growing economy as China in terms of national GDP contribution which amount up to 60% diversification of product, scale of assets and creation of employment.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) pronounce more in the private sector of the Nigeria economy. Almost all of them are starved of funds. The relative importance of the enterprises differs from one type of business to another. The major areas of business enterprises activities are in manufacturing, rendering services and product distribution. Banbeck (1983) as cited in Tambou (2018) posited that more than one-third of all the manufacturing firms in Nigeria employ fewer than five persons or none at all and that close to two-thirds employ fewer than twenty workers. His study on the whole revealed that five per cent of non-farm business of all kinds employs fewer than fifty workers each. The characteristics of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) largely constitute the basis of their problems and special needs that have attracted different authorities and sectors in recent past.

The development of Small Scale Business by the government is a move in the direction to increase economic growth. Ekpeyong and Nyong (1992) suggested that SSBs are organic part of a viable structure for sustainable economic development in less developed countries like Nigeria.

They have the tendency to produce greater benefits for the economy than large enterprises because they have higher multiplier effects. Ojo (2009) put forth one of the solutions to the problems of development in Nigeria is the promotion of entrepreneurial development scheme. A veritable way to do this is government promotion of small scale businesses. Entrepreneurship has been identified as vital for the continued vitality of the modern market for more businesses to emerge; hence, competition and economic growth are improved (Klapper and Love, 2011 as cited in Adeusi & Aluko, 2014, p. 86)

With these efforts, the Bayelsa State government in alleviating poverty and to raise a modest businesslike state went further to established the State Micro Finance and Enterprise Development Agency in 2014. The agency was formed to promote small and medium enterprise. Since formation the agency has carried out several empowerment programmes in reducing poverty in the state. The agency with its primary role of improving the wellbeing of the people in the state has embarked on several training programmes of SMEs and also carried out quarterly seminars, workshops for enterprises. More so, as part of the government funding scheme for small and medium enterprises development in Bayelsa state and in alleviating poverty towards even development, the agency has also partnered with national and international development agencies like: CBN, Bank of Industry, World Bank, India SME Forum in order to foster rapid development to the people.

Conceptual Clarification and Analysis

Small and Medium Enterprises

The unemployment conditions of Nigeria indicate that many individuals who are skilled, capable and willing to be engaged are unemployed or underemployed. The situation is an indication that opportunities are not available. In most countries, job opportunities are created by individuals who establish one form of business or the other as entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs are known to establish business and nurture them to become lofty ventures. In countries such as China, India, Japan, America, Germany and South Africa, entrepreneurs have taken the challenge of industrialization through the creation of small scale business, which help to create job opportunities there by reducing unemployment and to great extent poverty. Udu and Udu (2015, p.213).

Egbo(2009) supported the view that Small Scale enterprises have some common indicators such as the size of capital investment, value of annual turnover and number of paid employees. The need to develop a virile small business enterprise is increasingly being recognized by developing countries. SSEs boost employment as they employ a large number of people per unit of investment capital than the large-scale capital intensive enterprises. For Lubo (2019) small and medium enterprises are firms that are into sales of consumable goods and they are into finished products that help in the growth and development of organisations. Leader (2018) asserts that Small and Medium enterprises entails business ventures that involves few individuals towards the development of their organisation and the country the business exist.

SMEs are non-subsidiary, independent firms/organizations which employ fewer numbers of employees. This number varies across countries. According to the European Union (EU), SMEs

are categories of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises which employ fewer than 250 persons and which have an annual turnover not exceeding 50 million Euros. In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria in its monetary policies circular No. 22 of 1988 defined SMEs as enterprises which have an annual turnover not exceeding Five Hundred Thousand Naira (N500, 000). For the sake of clarity, the National Policy on Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) has given a clear distinction of enterprises, based on employment and Assets. SMEs are organizations which can best be described through their capital, scope and cost of projects, annual turnover, financial strength and number of employees amongst other things. Such organizations must and can be registered under any part of the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) in order to do business in Nigeria. Nevertheless, it is usually advised that SMEs register under Part B of the CAMA. (Uche, 2018).

Ogechukwu (2006) identifies more general and comprehensive criteria for defining small and medium scale enterprises in different countries to include number of employees, annual turnover, local operations, sales volumes, financial strength, managers and owners autonomy, relatively small markets compared to their industries and capital usually supplied by individual or shareholders. The factors that determine the performance and relevance of the SMEs include policy of the government such as regulation and deregulation, infrastructure, access to external finance, technology, competition and corruption in the business environment in which they operate (Cited in Clement, 2018).

Small and Medium Enterprises Development and its Characteristics

Ayyagari (2007) in Amagonou (2018) noted that small and medium scale enterprises have been long recognised as an instrument of economic growth and development. The growing recognition of this fact has led the World Bank group on SME's sector to ensure that it is the core element in its strategy to foster economic growth, employment generation and poverty alleviation.

Kurfi (2007) described SME as being characterized by the following:

1. Management. The initiators are managing it and they make decisions without consulting any superior persons(s). The proprietor/owner perform all management functions, with division of labour and functional delegation of responsibilities largely absent (Lewis, 1977).
2. Simple organisation structure. The organisation structure of most SSEs is simple due to small number of employees. The functions of management are common (basic) to all types and sizes, of SSE. However, the conditions under which they are performed vary considerably from one-man "operation" to a "linear organisation structure"
3. High percentage of business failure. Reactions adduced for their failure varies but included management related problems (inexperience, incompetence's, inefficiency, lack of support), individual problem (arrogance, lack of faith, behavioural problem), production problems, financial problems, tax problems and marketing problems. Others are indulgence in fraud and stealing natural calamities, negligence of entrepreneur, government policies and market competition.

4. Lack of specialized managers. There is shortage of specialized managers due to limited opportunities. This results in the owner exercising all levels of management functions.

5. Limited employees. Usually the average number of employees in most SSEs is about 10 persons. Thus the owner/proprietor knows the employees.

5. Low capital base. Most SSEs have difficulties in sourcing funds from stock Exchange and even commercial banks. The costs of sourcing fund may be too exorbitant for management of SSEs.

Olokoyo (1995) asserted that a small business has at least two of the following characteristics:

1. The managers are often the owners
2. An individual owner(s) or a small group furnishes capital
3. The area of operation is local (though market served need not be local)
4. Size within the industry is relatively small (in Egbo, 2009, p. 176)

Government Roles and impact of Funding Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria and Bayelsa State.

Small scale industry plays important and crucial roles in the industrial development of any country (Ahmed, 2006). According to Ojo (2009) small-scale industry has a better prospect for developing domestic economy through the generation of goods and services that propels the economy of Nigeria. The need to focus on small scale industry became important in Nigeria because it was a means of ensuring self-independence, job creation, and import substitution, effective and efficient utilization of local raw materials (Ojo, 2009). Small businesses in Nigeria contribute to employment and a path to entrepreneurship. The focus of small businesses has shifted from providing only social goods but as a vehicle to entrepreneurship (Thurik & Wenekers, 2004) Therefore, it serves as a source of job creation and economic growth. This may well be the reason policy makers in Nigeria pay attention to small businesses in Adisa, et al. (2014, p.5).

With the need to create massive employment and reduce poverty among the people, the Bayelsa State Microfinance and Enterprise Development Agency hosted the Africa SMS roundtable in 2014, 2018. The agency also gained international recognition by bagging the 2017 World SME Excellence Award at the Habitat Center in New Delhi, India during the 21st International Conference on SME's jointly organized by the World Association for Small and Medium Enterprises and Grant Thornton International in the "Organisation Category". It was observed that the Bayelsa State Micro-finance and Enterprise Development Agency was recognised as a champion in promotion, support and development of the micro, small and medium enterprises ecosystem. They particularly made reference to the agency's efforts at spearheading and attracting over N4 billion, which is equivalent to over \$10 million, to entrepreneurs in the sub-sector and also employing the mind of creating over 7,000 direct and indirect jobs to the people.

The Bayelsa State government established the State Micro Finance and Enterprise Development Agency to midwife and promote the SME in the state, it was established by law in April, 30 2014 since then it has kicked the ground running, and the agency since inception has carried out various schemes giving loans to women cooperatives in the state; and to stimulate the economy also government established the Izon-Ibe Micro-Finance Bank (IMFB) not just in Yenagoa, the state capital but in all the local government areas within the state and this efforts had helped to advance the existence of small and medium enterprises across the state and in relation to Nigeria. The state agency has provided awareness campaign to help the rural people informed on the need of small and medium enterprises development for even development, with this gesture the Bayelsa State Government has key into the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) window for the N2bn Micro Small and Medium Enterprise Development Fund MSMEDF and it has accessed over N1.5bn and Bayelsans are accessing the loan at a single digit interest of two per cent. The agency has opens window with Bank of Industry (BoI) for another N2 billion loan scheme and other international agencies, as well as collaboration with industrial donor agencies. Therefore, the agency is working in line with its mandate to develop and promote the SMEs development sector in the state and that in their vehicle is to stabilise the economy, by creating wealth, jobs, and also birth prosperity and economic development in Bayelsa.

The agency employs the following efforts in supporting small and medium enterprise development: The Bayelsa State government has accessed a loan from CBN at 20 per cent and land to the agency at nine per cent and through the Participating Financial Institutions (PFIs) such as Equator Micro-Finance Bank, Num Micro Finance Bank, Crystabel Micro-Finance Bank, Izon-Ibe Micro-Finance Bank, the loans are given single digit interest and that in the best any borrower can get and enjoy.

The agency creates a data base and also employed the know your customer approach in giving out the loans to beneficiaries and this aspect greatly help to foster a mutual understanding between the agency and the beneficiaries. The government has also embarked on programmes and policies geared towards the development of this sub-sector. These programmes include micro credit scheme, Bayelsa State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (BY-SEED), co-operative development Credit Scheme among others aimed at developing and enhancing the viability of the SMEs (Atalaowei, 2018,p.87).

Table showing Bayelsa State Micro Finance Banks across the Eight (8) Local Government Areas and the Head Agency of Bayelsa State Microfinance and Enterprises Development Agency (BYMEDA) and their Purposes and Activities .

Name of Banks /LGA	Activities /Programmes	Kick off / Remark
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Yenagoa	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to help the needy	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start but not fully implemented
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to

Southern-Ijaw	scale businesses	start / still at the implementation stage
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Sagbama	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to assist the poor / access loan to start up	25million was given by Bayelsa state government to start/ on going
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Ekeremor	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium scale businesses	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ programme not complemented
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Ogbia	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium scale businesses	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ yet to complete the programme
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Brass	Direct and access start up capital for small and medium scale businesses	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ still at the completion process
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Nembe	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to assist the poor and access start up capital	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ on going
Izon-Ebe Micro Finance Bank Kolokuma/Opukoma	Empowering the poor and providing valuable tool to assist the poor/ access loan	25million was given by the Bayelsa state government to start/ implementation process
Bayelsa State Microfinance and Enterprises Development Agency	Total number of beneficiaries (cooperatives and individuals) over 1500	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Bank of Industry (BIO) gave the agency 4.0 billion Naira to MSMEs/ ongoing

Source: Bayelsa Small and Medium Enterprises Bulletin 2019/2023

For Governor (2019) small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state has helped in the following ways; improving the living standard of people within the state, carrying out small business, keeping the people of the state always busy as regards to their respective businesses, making the government to recognized their business across the state, promoting the people businesses within the local communities.

Challenges Faced by Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria and Bayelsa State

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria has not performed very well. They have contributed just a small percentage of the GDP unlike the other emerging economies in the world. The challenges being faced by our own SMEs are very many. These challenges have been responsible for the slow growth of SMEs in Nigeria. Some of the major challenges include:

Poor managerial skills - From interaction with most SMEs especially the one-man business owners, the common problem is poor leadership. One main reason for this is lack of training and poor capacity building. Most people go into businesses without adequate knowledge or entrepreneurial skills on how to run businesses.

Poor or inadequate infrastructure - The poor state of infrastructure in the country has been a major obstacle to the growth of SMEs. Only few entrepreneurs can survive without power. The epileptic or irregular power supply has contributed significantly to the high cost of doing businesses in the country. Apart from power, lack of good access roads and other social amenities have also hindered the growth of SMEs.

Lack of access to funds- Most SMEs find it difficult to access funds or capital. Most Nigerian banks do not support start-ups and even existing businesses do not have the required collateral. For SMEs that go to non-conventional banks, the high interest rate is always a burden. The issue funding or finance, therefore, is a major challenge for SMEs in Nigeria.

Unfair competition- Most SMEs in Nigeria cannot compete with items or products from other countries especially China and other Asian tigers. The government has also not helped in this area because of dumping of fake and sub-standard goods, and smuggling activities in the country. When combined with the high cost of production in the country, locally made goods can hardly compete in the area of pricing.

Government Bureaucracy-Another challenge faced by SMEs is bureaucratic bottle neck of various government agencies like CAC, NAFDAC, and Customs etc. For instance, getting NAFDAC approval for food item or drug can take years. In most cases you spend 5 times the official price to facilitate the approval. You can spend as high as N250, 000 to get NAFDAC approval for just one product even after meeting all the specified requirements. Even with the recent government initiatives on ease of doing business, a lot still need to be done to address this issue.

Low Demand-In Nigeria, there is still preference for imported goods over locally made goods. Even government agencies and departments do not patronize our own SMEs. All these combined create marketing problems for SMEs in Nigeria. No wonder many of them closed down within the first few years of operation. No business can survive in the long run without enough sales to cover operational costs

Multiple Taxes and Levies- SMEs are subject to so many taxes and levies from local government to federal government. So many agents are involved in the collection of taxes and levies. This

has given room for unauthorized levies and taxes. The impact of this on the operational costs of SMEs cannot be overemphasized (As cited in Ojo, 2017).

The challenges of the SMEs are induced by the operating environment (government policy, globalization effects, financial institutions etc) others are functions of the nature and character of SMEs themselves. (Onugu, 2005 in Atalaowei,2018).

For Leader (2018) the existence of small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state faces many challenges and those problems greatly disturbed the smooth running of their businesses across the state. These challenges include:

- Lack of enough funds to carry out the enterprises - Government finds it difficult to provide enough fund for the Bayelsa small and medium enterprises in other to carry out their business effectively. Lack of adequate funds to a large extent affects the operation of SMEs in Bayelsa state. That is, the state government does not budgeted adequate funds to finance SMEs in the state and this greatly reduce the level of seriousness of the entrepreneurs.
- Government influences on whom to be given the loan- Another challenge is the issue of government overwhelming influence to who will benefit from the loan. That is, government used to select those who will be given the loan to execute the business at their direction. More so, loans are given to those who have direct link with the state government personnel's.
- Lack of training on how to manage the loan- SMEs are not usually trained on how to manage loans and business. Lack of training to a large extent lower their technical know-how in handling their enterprises
- Inability to access the next Tranche Loans from the CBN because of not recovering the 70 percent Returns- Another challenge facing government funding scheme on small and medium enterprises is the issue of accessing another trench of loans from CBN because the government is unable to get returns of 70 per cent returns from the entrepreneurs.
- Political instability – The change of leadership also affected the various enterprises in the state, for instance the entrepreneurs billed to be cleared by the previous government was cancelled by the current administration. Political instability to a large extent causes the smooth running of funding SMEs in the state.

Awini (2019) posited that funding small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa state is a difficult task all together. The operation of SMEs in Bayelsa state has the following challenges: lack of adequate funding from the state government to strengthen the smooth running of SMEs, government unfavourable policies on the means of accessing the loans by beneficiaries, poor awareness from the government to the owners of the various enterprises and the general public on the nature of loans and grants taking, problem of favouritism, nepotism and tribalism in giving out the loans, lack of planning on the time frame in disbursing the loans to beneficiaries, inability to train the entrepreneurs on the nature of their various businesses, another challenge is the delay in the implementation of budget, problem of record keeping and the improper management of information relating to grants, loans .

Theoretical Analysis

The framework of analysis used in this paper was the structural-functionalism which emerged through the writings of Herbert Spencer (1820-1930). Spencer believes that different parts within an organ function together in having a whole system to perform effectively and efficiently.

For Izugbara, (2004 ,p. 137) structural –functionalism assumes that social behaviour is structured in the sense that social interactions between members of a society are guided by laws and rules. Values provided the guidelines for social behaviour, and translate more concretely into specific directives in terms of statuses, roles and norms. The structure of society can be seen as the sum-total of normative behaviour. The parts of society; polity, educational system, economic system, religion, health, and familial system are major aspects of social structure. These parts are called social institutions and consist of interconnected, interrelated and interdependent roles. Structural-functionalism maintains that for any social structure to work, the various parts of the structure must fulfil their respective functions. Simply defined, function means effect. Thus the function of the family is the effect it has on society in general. Function also means the contribution of a given institution to the survival of the whole society. Society has certain basic needs which must be met if it is to survive; these are known as functional pre-requisites. It is the function of all these institution to satisfy their functional pre-requisites. From the structural-functionalist perspective, society is regarded as a system; for a system to survive, its constituents must be compatible and stable. This notion connotes value consensus, stability and solidarity.

Okoye (2012) Opines that the basic assumptions and postulations of the structural-functional framework are:

- It takes the society as a single, inter-connected system, each element of which performs a specific function. The basic feature of such a system is the interaction of its components for the maintenance of its equilibrium.
- If society is a system as a whole, it has parts that are interrelated. A social system has a dominant tendency towards stability that is maintained by virtue of built-in-mechanism. If there are deviations or tensions, they are resolved. Thus, change in a social system is not sudden or revolutionary, but gradual and adjustive.
- Underlying the whole social structure are broad aims and principles that are observed by the members of the society (Johari, 2005, p. 86-87).

In applying this theory to this research, it has been observed that government as one of the system consist of many parts/ structures and its numerous tasks in providing developmental needs of different people at different interval. More so, the study revealed that for government to provide funding scheme in reducing poverty to citizens through small and medium enterprises, many agencies like CBN, loan banks, and small and medium enterprises agency in the state would work together for the overall success of the stated goals of the government.

This process greatly account for coordination and implementation of the agency mission and vision in line with the policy of the Bayelsa state government, World bank, CBN, financial loan banks in carry out the small and medium enterprises activities in the state, because if

one part fails to deliver, then it would lead to poor implementation of the business activities in the state.

Methodology

The method employed in this research was the qualitative approach and it relied purely on secondary source of data collection and analysis towards the study of government funding scheme for small and medium enterprises development and the population was Nigeria, while the sample sized adopted was the Bayelsa state. The study used purposive sampling technique.

Findings and Conclusion

It was observed in the study that funding small and medium enterprises by the government to a large extent helps in the overall growth and development of the economy. Because the purpose of forming and funding small and medium enterprises is a way of adding to the increased of employment generation, a planned process and advance socio-economic growth, it helps in creating and advancing interdependent linkages with big companies across states , it pave ways to the act of improving the level of entrepreneurship, it also help to create and improve local savings between business owners , it help also to drastically bring down the high level of poverty that will geared towards the drive of sustainable development.

Findings also revealed that funding small and medium enterprises are difficult considering the conditions and criteria used in giving out the loans and the challenges like: government influence in giving out the loans, political instability, government policy, multiple taxes consideration, challenges from the government side to access other tranches, government bureaucracy, poor managerial skills and inadequate communication network. This position was clearly associated by Ojo (2017), Leader (2018), Atalaowei (2018) and Awini(2019) , when they posited that forming and funding small and medium enterprises in Nigeria and especially in Bayelsa state have help in promoting the Bayelsa state small and medium enterprises policy and this also helped to project the state globally.

The paper concludes that, government plays so many roles in funding small and medium enterprises and without government support; it would have being a great threat in doing small business in Bayelsa state. Government support in forming small and medium business has enabled the entrepreneurs to perform better and this has encouraged them to continue with the business. And the continues funding of small and medium enterprise by the government greatly serve as a catalyst for socio-economic development and its leads to positive impact on the people.

Recommendations

From the above findings, the study recommended the following:

1. There should be special budget provided by the government to fund small and medium enterprises in the state
2. Government should strengthen small and medium enterprises in all states for efficient mutual relationship for the development of various enterprises.
3. Government should revisit the procedures and steps used in accessing the loans, so that it will not be too stringent for entrepreneurs to access such fund.
4. Government should provide a medium of communication to enlighten the public of the importance small and medium enterprises on the use and purpose of the loans
5. The government should have a cordial relationship between the enterprises on training needs, workshops, and lectures on business
6. Government should establish more grants, loans agencies that will specifically fund small and medium enterprises in the state and country.
7. The state government should link up and collaborate with international donors to specifically fund small and medium enterprises in the state.

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